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EVALUATION OF ANTI ARTHRITIC ACTIVITY OF ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *PELTOPHORUM PTEROCARPUM* FLOWERS

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ABSTRACT

Peltophorum pterocarpum belongs to the family caesalpiniaceae and traditionally it is proved to be used in the treatment of stomatitis, insomnia, constipation, ringworm, dysentery, muscular pains, sores and skin disorders. The objective of the study is to evaluate the antiarthritic activity of ethanolic extract *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers by using protein denaturation method. The inhibition of protein denaturation was taken as a measure of the invitro anti-arthritic activity. The maximum percentage inhibition of protein denaturation for *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flower extracts were found to be 75.42±1.92%, 83.01±1.33% and 87.67±1.21% respectively at a dose of 600, 800, 1000 µg/ml. When compared to standard diclofenac sodium was found out to be 82.0±1.63%, 87.77±1.08% and 91.54±0.80% respectively at a dose of 600, 800, 1000 µg/ml. in conclusion the results support the use of ethanolic extract *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers in treating arthritis.

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INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, progressive and disabling autoimmune disease. It is affecting the joints and periarticular tissue. It can affect any joint and more commonly affecting the hands, feet and wrists ^[1]. Rheumatoid arthritis is a terrifying disease ^[2] and is capable of producing severe crippling deformities and functional disabilities. It commonly leads to significant disability, caused by number of proinflammatory molecules released by macrophages including reactive oxygen species and eicosanoids such as prostaglandins, leukotrienes and cytokines ^[3].

Inflammatory form of arthritis is rheumatoid arthritis which attacks the synovial membrane resulting in swelling and pain ^[4]. It is a complex process involving synovial cell proliferation and fibrosis, pannus formation and cartilage and bone erosion. The process of rheumatoid arthritis is mediated by an interdependent network of cytokines, prostanooids and proteolytic enzymes. Arachidonic acid metabolism is modulated by inhibiting enzymes like COX and LOX. These are the potential target for chronic inflammatory conditions ^[5]. Interleukin-6 (IL-6) is an inflammatory cytokine which is involved in inflammation, immunity, endocrine functions and particularly it is a major regulator of the synthesis of acute phase reactants by the liver. IL-6 is produced by different cells in the body including lymphocytes, monocyte, fibroblasts and endothelial cells. Adipose tissue is another major source of IL-6. Excessive adipose tissue deposition leads to excessive production of IL-6, which is a high risk factor to the RA which belongs to an auto immune disorder ^[6-9].

Peltophorum pterocarpum is a common deciduous tree belongs to the family caesalpiaceae, grown in tropical countries. Different names of this plant are Yellow Poinciana, golden flame, copper pod, Rusty shield bearer and Yellow flamboyant. Different parts of this plant are usefull to treat many diseases like stomatitis, insomnia, skin troubles and constipation. The flower extract is known to be a good sleep inducer and used in insomnia treatment. Bark is used as a medicine for dysentery and can also be used to prepare eye lotions and to treat pains and sores ^[10]. Stem infusion used to treat dysentery, gargles, tooth powder and to reduce muscle pain. The flowers are used as astringent to relive intestinal disorders after pain at child birth, sprains and to treat swelling. The flowers of these plants are the rich sources of carotinoids ^[11]. The chemical constituents of this plant are known to exhibit several biological activities such as anti microbial activity, anti oxidant activity, cytotoxic activity, anti glyceic activity, aldose reductase inhibition activity, cardiotoxic activity, choline esterase inhibitory activity, etc..^[12-17]. The present objective of the study is to evaluation of the antiarthritic activity of ethanolic extravt *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers by using protein denaturation method.

Figure 1: *Peltophorum pterocarpum* tree.

Figure 2: Flowers of *Peltophorum pterocarpum*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of flowers and authentication

The fresh flowers of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* were collected from the village Peddasettypalli, Proddatur, Kadapa district, Andhra Pradesh, India, in the month of April 2014. The plant was authenticated by Dr. Madhav chetty, Taxonomist, S.V. University, Tirupathi, India. The flowers were shade dried at room temperature and the shade dried flowers were powdered through rotary grinder.

Extraction of flowers of *Peltophorum pterocarpum*

Finely powdered flower sample (500 gm) was packed in Soxhlet apparatus for extraction with 400 ml of 70 % ethanol until it does not show the presence of any residue on evaporation. Solvents were removed from the extracts with the help of rotary vacuum evaporator.

Preparation of egg albumin

Principle

Albumin, the water soluble protein, is isolated from egg white by salting out technique. Globulins precipitate at half saturation, while albumins precipitate at full saturation with ammonium sulphate salt. Proteins in solution form hydrogen bonds with the surrounding aqueous milieu, through their exposed polar/ionic functional groups. When high concentration of small and highly charged ions such as ammonium and sulphate are added to protein solutions, they compete with protein for binding with water molecules. This interaction lowers the solubility of proteins, resulting in their precipitation. This forms the basis of the isolation of egg albumin.

Procedure

- (i) Collect egg white from eggs carefully, avoiding the egg yolk, into a 500 ml beaker. Dilute the egg white to 100 ml by adding distilled water with vigorous beating and stirring. Any precipitate (of ovomucoid) formed at this stage is removed by centrifugation. Add 32.5 g of solid ammonium sulphate in small proportions at room temperature with gentle stirring (avoid frothing). Equilibrate the contents for 15 minutes at room temperature. The precipitate formed is that of globulins, which is removed by filtration or centrifugation.
- (ii) Saturate the filtrate or the supernatant by adding solid ammonium sulphate (35.5 g). Leave the contents at room temperature for 30 minutes with intermittent stirring. The albumin precipitate formed is recovered by centrifugation. Dissolve the precipitate in minimum volume of distilled water and dialyse the protein solution extensively in cold, against distilled water in 2 L plastic beaker (two to three changes of distilled water over a period 36-48 hours) so as to remove the salt (test the presence of ammonium sulphate in water by adding barium chloride solution (5% w/v) (a white precipitate of barium sulphate is observed). Measure the volume of protein solution after dialysis and add 0.05 % w/v sodium azide as preservative. Store the protein solution in cold temperature^[18].

Preparation of test sample

Samples for experiments were prepared by dissolving extract to obtain a stock solution of 100 mg/ml, from the stock solution, different working dilutions were prepared to get concentration range of 100, 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000 µg/ml of ethanolic extracts. Diclofenac sodium is a standard drug. The concentration of standard drug was prepared in 100, 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000 µg/ml.

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer Saline (pH 6.3)

Dissolve 8 g of sodium chloride (NaCl), 0.2 g of potassium chloride (KCl), 1.44 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4), 0.24 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4) in 800 ml distilled water. The pH was adjusted to 6.3 using 1N HCl and make up the volume to 1000 ml with distilled water^[19].

Protein denaturation by using Egg albumin

The reaction mixture (5 ml) consisted of 0.2 ml of egg albumin (from fresh hen's egg), 2.8 ml of phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 6.4) and 2 ml of varying concentrations of ethanolic extract of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers (EEPP) so that final concentrations become 100, 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000 µg/ml.

Similar volume of distilled water served as control. Then the mixtures were incubated at $(37 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$ in a BOD incubator for 15 min and then heated at 70°C for 5 min. After cooling, their absorbance was measured at 660 nm. Diclofenac sodium was used as standard drug.

The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated by using the following formula^[20].

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = (\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}) \times 100 / \text{Abs control}$$

Abs = Absorbance

Statistical analysis

All values were expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) of three replicate experiments and were analyzed using the GraphPad program (GraphPad, San Diego, CA, USA).

RESULTS

The production of auto antigen in arthritic disease may be due to denaturation of protein, membrane lysis and proteinase action. The maximum percentage inhibition of protein denaturation for Diclofenac sodium were observed to be 60.37%, 68.86%, 77.35%, 82.0%, 87.77 and 91.54 %, and for 70% ethanolic extract of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers (EPPP) were observed to be 47.16%, 61.32%, 68.86%, 75.47 %, 83.01% and 87.67% at 100, 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Diclofenac sodium and EPPP respectively. The values are shown in Table 1 and it is graphically represented in Figure 5. Figure 3 and 4 representing the test tubes containing reaction mixture before and after incubation.

Figure 3: Before Incubation.

Figure 4: After Incubation.

Table 1: Invitro anti arthritic effect of ethanolic extract of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers.

S.No.	Groups	Concentration (mg/ml)	Absorbance (nm)	% inhibition
1	Control	---	0.106±0.002	---
2	Standard (Diclofenac Trated group)	100	0.042±0.003	60.37±3.70
		200	0.033±0.004	68.86±3.52
		400	0.024±0.003	77.35±2.63
		600	0.019±0.004	82.0±1.63
		800	0.013±0.003	87.77±1.08
		1000	0.009±0.003	91.54±0.80
3	Test (70 % EEPP)	100	0.056±0.003	47.16±3.39
		200	0.041±0.003	61.32±2.73
		400	0.033±0.001	68.86±2.16
		600	0.026±0.001	75.47±1.92
		800	0.018±0.002	83.01±1.33
		1000	0.012±0.002	87.67±1.21

All values represent Mean ±SEM; n= 3 in each group.

Figure 5: Invitro anti arthritic effect of EEPP on protein denaturation method comparing Concentration Vs % Inhibition.

DISCUSSION

The *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers were extracted with ethanol. The knowledge of the chemical constituents of plants helps to screen for biological activities. The phenolic and flavanoids are widely distributed secondary metabolites in plants having anti-oxidant activity and have wide range of biological activities as anti-apoptosis, anti-aging, anti carcinogen, anti-inflammation, anti-atherosclerosis, cardiovascular protection and improvement of endothelial function, as well as inhibition of angiogenesis and cell proliferation activities^[21].

Denaturation of tissue proteins is one of the well documented causes of inflammatory and arthritic diseases. Production of auto-antigens in certain arthritic diseases may be due to denaturation of proteins in vivo. The mechanism of denaturation probably involves alteration of electrostatic hydrogen, hydrophobic and disulphide bonding. The increments in absorbance of plant extract and reference drug with respect to control indicated the stabilization of albumin protein. This anti-denaturation effect was further supported by the change in viscosities. It has been reported that the viscosities of protein solutions increase on denaturation^[22].

From the results of our study reveals that EEPP are capable of controlling the production of auto antigen and inhibits denaturation of protein in rheumatic disease which may be due to the presence of phenolic and flavanoid compounds

CONCLUSION

Inhibition of protein denaturation was studied to establish the mechanism of anti-arthritic effect of Ethanolic extract of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers. Therefore, our present in-vitro studies on EEPP demonstrated the significant anti-arthritic activity. The presence of active principles such as flavonoids, tannins and phenolic compounds may responsible for this activity.

Further studies are necessary to isolate and reveal the active compound which is responsible for its antiarthritic activity, present in the ethanolic extract of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* flowers.

Acknowledgments & Conflict of Interests:

None

ABBREVIATIONS

EEPP	- Ethanolic Extravt <i>Peltophorum Pterocarpum</i>
RA	- Rheumatoid arthritis
COX	- Cyclooxygenase
LOX	- Lipoxygenase
IL 6	- Interleukin-6
PBS	- Phosphate buffered saline

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